

TAX VOLUNTEERS MEDIATE E-FILING SYSTEMS AND TAX KNOWLEDGE FOR INDIVIDUAL TAXPAYER COMPLIANCE

VEBRY M LUMBAN GAOL^{1*}, CHRISTNOVA HASUGIAN²,
HAMONANGAN SIALLAGAN³, HERTI DIANA HUTAPEA⁴ and
AGUS MULIANA LAOLI⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Universitas HKBP Nommensen.

*Corresponding Author Email: vebry.lumbangaol@uhn.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the role of Tax Volunteers in mediating the influence of the e-filing system and tax knowledge on the compliance of individual taxpayers in Deli Serdang Regency. The background of this study is based on the low level of taxpayer compliance in Indonesia, despite the modernization of tax administration through the e-filing system and various efforts to improve tax literacy through the Tax Volunteer program. This study uses a quantitative approach with the Partial Least Squares – Structural Equation Modeling (SEM-PLS) method processed using SmartPLS version 4.0. The research population consists of individual taxpayers registered at the Lubuk Pakam Tax Office (KPP) who have interacted with Tax Volunteers. The sampling technique used purposive sampling with a total of 100 taxpayer respondents. Data were collected through the distribution of questionnaires using a 1–5 Likert scale and analyzed through outer model testing (validity and reliability) and inner model testing (hypothesis testing and mediation testing). The results of the study show that: (1) The e-filing system has a positive and significant effect on taxpayer compliance with a coefficient value of 0.351 and a *p-value* of 0.000; (2) Tax knowledge has a positive and significant effect on taxpayer compliance with a coefficient of 0.194 and a *p-value* of 0.010; (3) Tax volunteers partially mediate the effect of the e-filing system on taxpayer compliance with an *indirect effect* value of 0.087 and a *p-value* of 0.007; and (4) Tax volunteers partially mediate the effect of tax knowledge on taxpayer compliance with an *indirect effect* value of 0.398 and a *p-value* of 0.000. These findings indicate that the presence of Tax Volunteers can strengthen the influence of the e-filing system and tax knowledge on taxpayer compliance. Thus, the synergy between digital taxation transformation, increased tax literacy, and social participation through Tax Volunteers has proven effective in improving sustainable tax compliance.

Keywords: E-Filing System, Tax Knowledge, Tax Volunteers, Taxpayer Compliance, SEM- PLS.

INTRODUCTION

Taxes are one of the main sources of revenue for the state, which serves to finance various development programs and public services (Kesumasari & Suardana, 2018). In Indonesia, taxes play a very important role in supporting national development, both in terms of infrastructure, education, health, and community welfare. However, despite the crucial role of taxes, the level of taxpayer compliance, especially among individual taxpayers (WPOP), remains a significant challenge.

According to Amran (2018), taxpayer income is the income that taxpayers earn from their work. Individual taxpayer income is usually obtained from their main job or side jobs, such as freelance work. Based on data from the Indonesian Directorate General of Taxes (DJP), there has been an increase in the number of ITPs reporting Annual Tax Returns (SPT) in recent

years. For example, the Bangkalan Tax Office recorded that during a certain period, there were 35,709 ITP Annual Tax Returns reported on time. Although this figure shows an increase in compliance, many taxpayers still experience difficulties in reporting taxes, especially in the use of technology such as *e-filing*, Dewi and Merkusiwati (2018) Although this figure shows an increase in compliance, many taxpayers still experience difficulties in reporting taxes, especially in the use of technology such as *e-filing*. This shows that despite efforts to increase tax awareness and compliance, there are still challenges that need to be overcome. Adnyana, I. M. D., & Yuesti, A. (2020)

One of the main factors affecting compliance rates is the low number of tax volunteers among the public. Previous studies have shown that tax volunteers have not had a significant impact on improving tax performance. Although there is a positive relationship between compliance and tax volunteers, this indicates the need for more effective mechanisms or approaches to bridge the gap between tax volunteers and compliance.

Table: Compliance Level of Individual Taxpayers (WP OP) at KPP Pratama Lubuk Pakam

Year	Registered Individual Taxpayers	Individual Taxpayers Filing Tax Returns	Individual Taxpayers Not Filing Tax Returns	Compliance Rate of Individual Taxpayers
2021	311,413	81,253	230,160	26.09%
2022	341,621	87,344	254,277	25.56%
2023	370,127	74,704	295,423	20.18%
2024	397,910	69,205	328,705	17.39%

Source: KPP Pratama Lubuk Pakam

From the data in the table above, it can be seen that each year the number of registered taxpayers has increased from 311,413 WP OP in 2021 to 397,910 WP OP in 2024. However, the compliance rate ratio actually shows a significant decline. In 2021, the compliance ratio reached 26.09% with 81,253 WP OP reporting tax returns out of a total of 311,413 active WP OP. However, this figure continued to decline, reaching its lowest point in 2024, with a compliance ratio of only 17.39%, where out of 397,910 active WP OP, only 69,205 WP OP reported their tax returns. This decline in compliance rates is even more alarming when considering that the number of individual taxpayers who did not file tax returns increased from 230,160 in 2021 to 328,705 in 2024. This phenomenon raises questions about the effectiveness of the e-filing system in improving taxpayer compliance, considering that this system is supposed to facilitate tax return reporting.

The E-Filing system is a technological innovation that allows taxpayers to file their tax returns online, anytime and anywhere, without having to visit the tax office in person. E-filing offers various advantages such as convenience, speed, cost efficiency, and accuracy of information

submitted. With this system, it is hoped that the tax reporting process will become more practical and increase taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their obligations. However, technological convenience does not necessarily guarantee a high level of compliance. One of the challenges that still exists is the low level of tax literacy and knowledge among individual taxpayers. Tax knowledge, both procedural (knowing how) and declarative (knowing that), plays a significant role in shaping taxpayer compliance behavior. Taxpayers who understand tax rules and procedures tend to be more capable and willing to fulfill their obligations in a timely and correct manner. To bridge the gap in tax knowledge and skills, the DGT collaborates with universities to form Charge Centers that give birth to the Tax Volunteer program. Tax volunteers are individuals, generally students, who voluntarily provide education, assistance, and guidance to taxpayers, particularly in filing tax returns through e-filing. This program aims to improve public tax literacy and overcome the limited number of tax officers available to provide direct education. Tax volunteers act as an extension of the tax authority in providing services, ranging from education and assistance with tax return filing to the activation of Electronic Filing Identification Numbers (EFIN). Thus, tax volunteers not only increase taxpayers' knowledge of taxation but also help overcome technical barriers in the use of e-filing, which in turn is expected to increase compliance among individual taxpayers.

In this context, Tax Volunteers emerge as one of the solutions to increase awareness and compliance among individual taxpayers. Tax Volunteers act as facilitators between the Directorate General of Taxes (DGT) and the community. However, they not only provide education on tax obligations but also provide assistance in annual tax return reporting and disseminate information on the latest tax policies. With the Tax Volunteer program, it is hoped that taxpayers will better understand their tax obligations and be encouraged to be more compliant in fulfilling them. Tax Volunteers are individuals who voluntarily contribute their time, energy, thoughts, and expertise to play an active role in tax education activities.

Tax volunteers are one form of tax education activity covered by the theme of increasing tax knowledge and skills, as stated in Article 1 point 9 of the Director General of Taxes Regulation No. PER-12/PJ/2021 concerning Tax Education. The tax volunteer program is carried out in accordance with Official Memorandum No. ND1317/J.09/2019 in order to promote third-party participation in tax extension operations and increase tax compliance. In this case, the tax volunteer program focuses on students under the auspices of tax centers or taxation study programs (partner organizations) throughout Indonesia. Tax centers or partner organizations are institutions at universities that function as centers for research, education, training, and socialization of taxation to the campus environment, taxpayers, and the community independently.

In addition, a study at the Blora Tax Office also found that Tax Volunteers are able to increase taxpayer compliance through direct service and the professionalism of volunteers in providing education to the community. This study emphasizes the importance of a community-based approach in increasing taxpayer awareness and compliance. However, there are also studies that do not agree with these findings. Darmayasa's (2020) study states that the e-filing system and tax volunteers have not had a significant impact on tax compliance in Indonesia, even though

there is a positive relationship between the two. This study raises the question of whether tax volunteers need mediators such as Tax Volunteers to have an impact on compliance levels.

The Tax Volunteer Program has proven to be effective in increasing taxpayer awareness and compliance. At the Jakarta Tamansari Tax Office, for example, this program successfully helped taxpayers who had difficulty using the *e-filing* system before the annual tax return reporting deadline (Daeng, R. R., & Mahmudi, 2022). The volunteers provided direct support to taxpayers by explaining the reporting steps in detail and helping them complete the reporting process properly. As a result, taxpayer satisfaction with taxation services increased significantly (Anakotta, F. M., Sapulette, S. G., & Iskandar, T. E. 2023).

However, challenges remain. One of them is taxpayers' lack of understanding of the modern taxation system and information technology used in tax reporting. Many taxpayers feel confused or uncertain about using the *e-filing* system, Djo, K. Y. W. (2022), so they prefer not to report at all or to report manually even though technology offers convenience. (Anisa and Suprajotno, 2020) In this context, Tax Volunteers play an important role as a liaison between the DGT and the community.

They not only provide information but also build trust between taxpayers and tax agencies. This program aims to educate the public about the importance of paying taxes and its impact on national development. With a more personal and interactive approach, it is hoped that the public's understanding of tax obligations will increase.

Based on the above phenomenon, this research is highly relevant to explore the role of Tax Volunteers as mediators between tax volunteers and WPOP compliance. By filling the research gap related to the effectiveness of tax volunteers on compliance through Tax Volunteer intervention, this research is expected to provide practical contributions to taxation policy in Indonesia.

Through this research, it is hoped that new strategies can be found to increase taxpayer awareness and compliance in Indonesia and strengthen the role of Tax Volunteers as a bridge between the government and the community in order to achieve the common goal of creating a more fair and transparent taxation system. This study is also expected to provide recommendations for the DGT to optimize the Tax Volunteer program so that it can be more effective in increasing WPOP compliance in the future.

Thus, this research will not only be beneficial for the development of knowledge in the field of taxation but also for better public policy-making related to tax management in Indonesia.

Research Questions

- 1) Does the e-filing system affect taxpayer compliance?
- 2) Does tax knowledge affect taxpayer compliance?
- 3) Can tax volunteers mediate the effect of the e-filing system on taxpayer compliance?
- 4) Can tax volunteers mediate the effect of tax knowledge on taxpayer compliance?

THEORY

Theory of Planned Behavior

Initially, this theory was called *the Theory of Reasoned Action* (TRA), which is a theory aimed at studying and predicting individual behavior in more specific terms. This theory was proposed in 1975 by Fishbein and Ajzen. In 1985, Ajzen developed this theory into *the Theory of Planned Behavior* (TPB). Ajzen argued that the main factor of an individual's primary behavior is the individual's intention (*Behavior Intention*) towards a particular behavior. In other words, an individual's behavior is driven by their intention to behave (Ajzen, 1991; Boediono et al., 2018). Intention is a motivation for behavior and action that can predict what a behavior will do if the intention is known. There are three factors that can influence the intention to behave, namely: 1. *Behavioral beliefs*, which are an individual's beliefs about the results of a behavior and the evaluation of those results (*beliefs strength and outcome evaluation*). 2. *Normative beliefs*, which are beliefs about the normative expectations of others and the motivation to meet those expectations (*normative beliefs and motivation to comply*). 3. *Control beliefs*, which are beliefs about the existence of things that support or inhibit the behavior to be displayed (*control beliefs*) and the perception of how strong the things that support and inhibit the behavior are (*perceived power*).

Attribution Theory

Attribution Theory is a theory proposed by Fritz Heider in 1958 that explains the understanding of a person's reaction to events around them, by knowing their reasons for the events they experience. Attribution theory studies the process of how a person interprets an event, studying how a person interprets the reasons or causes of their behavior. This theory was developed to explain the different ways of judging people, depending on the meaning attributed to a particular behavior. Heider states that behavioral attribution consists of two sources, namely (1) internal attribution or dispositional attribution, and (2) external attribution or environmental attribution (Moyer et al., 1958; H. Purba, 2021). In internal attribution, the actor concludes that behavior is caused by certain traits. Kodoati (2016) argues that behavior that arises internally is behavior that is under the personal control of the person concerned, while behavior that arises externally is behavior that is influenced by external parties, meaning that the individual concerned will be forced to behave due to the influence of the situation.

Definition of Taxation

In accordance with Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 28 of 2007 concerning General Provisions and Tax Procedures Article 1 point 1, Tax is a mandatory contribution to the state owed by individuals or entities that is enforceable by law, without receiving direct compensation and used for state purposes for the greatest prosperity of the people. According to Prof. Dr. Rochmat Soemitro, S.H (in Halim et al., 2018), tax is a contribution from the people to the state treasury based on law (which can be enforced) without receiving any direct reciprocal service (consideration) that can be demonstrated and is used to pay for public expenditures. Meanwhile, according to S. I. Djajadiningrat (Halim et al., 2018), tax is an obligation to surrender part of one's wealth to the state treasury due to certain circumstances,

events, and actions, which give a certain status, but not as a punishment, according to regulations set by the government and can be enforced, but there is no direct service in return from the state, to maintain the state in general.

E-Filing System

The implementation of the e-Filing System is a process or method that utilizes a predetermined system to submit or report Annual Tax Returns (SPT) electronically or online, which can be done anytime and anywhere (realtime) through the official DJP Online website (Novianti et al., 2023). E-filing is one of the steps in the modernization of tax administration services that aims to simplify the process of compiling and submitting SPT reports to the Directorate General of Taxes (DJP). It is hoped that the implementation of the e-filing system will increase the satisfaction and convenience felt by taxpayers, thereby indirectly encouraging taxpayer compliance. *E-Filing* is defined as a method of submitting annual tax return notifications or updates *online* and *in real-time* through the *DJP Online* website or using an application published by an Application Service Provider, namely ASP (Situmeang & Pesireron, 2021). *E-Filing* is designed for the convenience and comfort of taxpayers, allowing reporting to be done anytime and anywhere. This saves costs and time in the process of calculating, filling out, and submitting tax returns. Tax Volunteers are a form of cooperation between the Tax Authority and universities as a form of tax awareness inclusion aimed at serving the community (Eliza et al., 2022).

Tax Knowledge

According to Hardiningsih (2016), tax knowledge is the process of changing the attitudes and behavior of a taxpayer or group of taxpayers in an effort to mature people through teaching and training. Knowledge of tax regulations among the community through formal and non-formal education will have a positive impact on taxpayer compliance. Based on the above definition, it can be concluded that taxpayer knowledge is a process whereby taxpayers learn about taxation and apply that knowledge to pay taxes. The taxpayer knowledge referred to is understanding the general provisions and procedures of taxation (KUP), which include how to submit a Tax Return (SPT), payment, place of payment, fines, and deadlines for payment or SPT reporting.

Tax Volunteers

Referring to Article 1 point 9 of the Director General of Taxes Regulation No. PER-12/PJ/2021, a tax volunteer is someone who voluntarily contributes their time, energy, thoughts, and expertise to play an active role in tax education activities. These tax volunteers are one form of tax education activity covered by the theme of increasing tax knowledge and skills or Theme II (Article 4 paragraph (1), Article 6 paragraph (3) PER-12/PJ/2021). Based on Official Memorandum No. ND – 1317/ J.09/2019, the tax volunteer program is implemented to improve services, taxpayer compliance, and encourage the involvement of third parties in tax outreach activities. This tax volunteer program targets students from all majors, both with and without a background in taxation. This activity is carried out by involving tax centers or tax study programs (partner organizations) throughout Indonesia. These organizations carry out

tax volunteer activities ranging from publicity, registration, training, to the selection of tax volunteers. Meanwhile, the DGT regional office compiles a schedule of utilization activities along with the locations and number of volunteers needed.

In this study, researchers are interested in combining the roles of tax volunteers and electronic reporting in an effort to overcome these problems. They also want to prove how *public trust* mediates the influence of *E-Filing* and tax volunteers in increasing taxpayer compliance by building *public trust* through effective communication strategies, as part of the government's efforts to increase tax revenue.

Taxpayer Compliance

According to Gunadi (2005), taxpayer compliance is defined as follows: "Taxpayer compliance is when taxpayers are willing to fulfill their tax obligations in accordance with applicable regulations without the need for audits, thorough investigations, warnings or threats, and the application of legal or administrative sanctions." Meanwhile, E. Eliyani (1989), as quoted by Jatmiko (2006), states that taxpayer compliance is defined as submitting and reporting the required information on time, correctly filling in the amount of tax owed, and paying taxes on time without coercion. Non-compliance arises when one of the conditions of the definition is not met.

RESEARCH METHOD

Jenis, Research Design

This research is quantitative in nature, where data collection takes the form of numbers and the results of the research are analyzed using statistical calculations. The research design used is a *hypothesis testing study* to test the influence between the variables hypothesized in the research. The primary data source in this study was obtained directly from individual taxpayers registered at the Lubuk Pakam Tax Office using a questionnaire survey. Meanwhile, the secondary data in this study was obtained from the Directorate General of Taxes in the form of reports, journals, internet searches, and results from previous studies.

Research Population and Sample

The population in this study consisted of active registered individual taxpayers and e-filing certificate holders at the Lubuk Pakam Primary Tax Office, totaling 397,910 individual taxpayers. The targets in this study were individual taxpayers working in government and private institutions. The sample size was determined using the Slovin formula, namely:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Explanation:

N = Population size

n = Sample size

e = Margin of error (the acceptable level of error) from the population size (10%)

Based on data from the Lubuk Pakam Tax Office, the population of individual taxpayers is 397,910 people. Thus, the sample size in this study is:

$$\frac{397.910}{1+397.910 (0,1)^2} = 99.99 = 100$$

The number of samples taken in this study was 99.99, rounded up to 100 individual taxpayers.

Data Collection Techniques

The data collection technique used in this study was to distribute questionnaires. The data collection technique was through questionnaires containing a list of statements that were distributed directly to taxpayers registered at the Lubuk Pakam Tax Office and holders of *e-filing* certificates who were encountered *accidentally*, especially those working in government and private institutions. The questionnaire is a closed-ended questionnaire, meaning that respondents can only provide the answers provided.

Data Analysis

The data analysis method used in this study is *Partial Least Square* (PLS)-SEM using SmartPLS version 4.0 software . PLS is a *Structural Equation Modeling* (SEM) equation model based on components or variants. PLS is an alternative approach that shifts from a covariance-based SEM approach to a variant-based approach (Ghozali, 2015) .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The object of this study is individual taxpayers. Based on the respondent data contained in the questionnaire provided, the first stage in analyzing the research data is descriptive statistical analysis. Descriptive analysis is used to describe the maximum, minimum, and average values of each research variable used. The tools used to describe the variables in this study are the minimum, maximum, average (*mean*), and standard deviation values.

Table 4: Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
E-Filing System	100	3	5	3.91	0.639
Taxpayer Knowledge	100	2	5	4.00	0.731
Tax Volunteers	100	2	5	3.95	0.673
Taxpayer Compliance	100	2	5	4.04	0.738
Valid N (listwise)	100				0.731

Source: Primary data processed in 2025

From the table above, it can be seen that the lowest and highest scores for each variable are 2 and 5. For standard deviation, the lowest value is found in the e-filing system variable with a value of 0.391. Meanwhile, the highest value is found in the taxpayer knowledge variable.

The second stage is testing the research data instruments. Before conducting the analysis with *Partial Least Square* (PLS), the validity and reliability of the measuring instrument, namely the questionnaire, are tested. The validity test is intended to determine whether the measuring instrument used is truly appropriate for measuring the object (instrument) being measured. Meanwhile, the reliability test aims to determine the reliability of the measuring instrument or, in other words, whether the measuring instrument is consistent when used to measure the same object more than twice. The results of the validity and reliability testing of the instruments for each variable can be described as follows:

Table of Validity Test Results

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	P value	Description
E-Filing System (X1)	X1.1	0.849	<0.001	Valid
	X1.2	0.833	<0.001	Valid
	X1.3	0.887	<0.001	Valid
	X1.4	0.762	<0.001	Valid
	X1.5	0.790	<0.001	Valid
	X1.6	0.817	<0.001	Valid
	X1.7	0.823	<0.001	Valid
	X1.8	0.710	<0.001	Valid
	X1.9	0.779	<0.001	Valid
Tax Knowledge (X2)	X2.1	0.863	<0.001	Valid
	X2.2	0.756	<0.001	Valid
	X2.3	0.827	<0.001	Valid
	X2.4	0.794	<0.001	Valid
	X2.5	0.789	<0.001	Valid
	X2.6	0.856	<0.001	Valid
	X2.7	0.888	<0.001	Valid
Tax Volunteer (M)	M1.1	0.839	<0.001	Valid
	M1.2	0.781	<0.001	Valid
	M1.3	0.811	<0.001	Valid
	M1.4	0.775	<0.001	Valid
	M1.5	0.767	<0.001	Valid
	M1.6	0.848	<0.001	Valid
	M1.7	0.807	<0.001	Valid
Taxpayer Compliance (Y)	Y1.1	0.807	<0.001	Valid
	Y1.2	0.742	<0.001	Valid
	Y1.3	0.888	<0.001	Valid
	Y1.4	0.866	<0.001	Valid
	Y1.5	0.871	<0.001	Valid
	Y1.6	0.840	<0.001	Valid
	Y1.7	0.838	<0.001	Valid

Source: Primary data processed, 2025

The test results in the table above show that all outer loadings of the construct indicators have values above 0.5 and P values < 0.05, so it can be concluded that these measurements meet the convergent validity requirements. The *composite reliability* test aims to test the validity of instruments in a research model specifically for reflexive indicators.

The *composite reliability* test results are presented in the following table:

Table 6: Composite Reliability Test Results

No	Variable	Composite Reliability	Description
1	E-Filing System	0.933	Reliable
2	Taxpayer Knowledge	0.928	Reliable
3	Tax Volunteers	0.922	Reliable
4	Taxpayer Compliance	0.909	Reliable

Source: Processed primary data, 2025

Table 6 shows that the *composite reliability* value of all variables is greater than 0.70. This means that the indicators used in this study are reliable or consistent. Thus, it can be concluded that all indicators are indeed measures of their respective constructs.

The factor loading (*outer loading*) value shows the weight of each indicator as a measure of each variable. The largest factor loading indicates that the indicator is the most dominant measure of the variable, and vice versa. The factor loading results for the indicators of taxpayer knowledge, tax socialization, taxpayer awareness, and taxpayer compliance are as follows:

Table 7: Outer Loading Values of Research Variables

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	P value
E-Filing System (X1)	X1.1	0.849	<0.001
	X1.2	0.833	<0.001
	X1.3	0.887	<0.001
	X1.4	0.762	<0.001
	X1.5	0.790	<0.001
	X1.6	0.817	<0.001
	X1.7	0.823	<0.001
	X1.8	0.710	<0.001
	X1.9	0.779	<0.001
Tax Knowledge (X2)	X2.1	0.863	<0.001
	X2.2	0.756	<0.001
	X2.3	0.827	<0.001
	X2.4	0.794	<0.001
	X2.5	0.789	<0.001
	X2.6	0.856	<0.001
	X2.7	0.888	<0.001
Tax Volunteers (M)	M1.1	0.839	<0.001
	M1.2	0.781	<0.001
	M1.3	0.811	<0.001
	M1.4	0.775	<0.001
	M1.5	0.767	<0.001
	M1.6	0.848	<0.001
Taxpayer Compliance (Y)	M1.7	0.807	<0.001
	Y1.1	0.807	<0.001
	Y1.2	0.742	<0.001
	Y1.3	0.888	<0.001
	Y1.4	0.866	<0.001

	Y1.5	0.871	<0.001
	Y1.6	0.840	<0.001
	Y1.7	0.838	<0.001

Source: Primary data processed in 2025

Empirical analysis using the *Warp Partial Least Square* (Warp PLS) model shows that nine indicators significantly form the e-filing system variable and measure taxpayer knowledge. The factor loading values of the tax knowledge variable indicators show that the seven indicators significantly form the factor loading values of the taxpayer knowledge variable. The factor loading values of the tax volunteer variable indicators show that the seven indicators significantly form the tax volunteer variable. Meanwhile, the factor loading values of the taxpayer compliance variable indicators based on the table above can be interpreted as showing that the seven indicators significantly form the taxpayer compliance variable, with the payment indicator dominantly forming the taxpayer compliance variable.

Hypothesis Testing and Intervening Effects

The results of hypothesis testing using the *Partial Least Square* (WarpPLS) structural equation model show that the direct effects of all hypotheses are significant and the indirect effects of all hypotheses are also significant. Hypothesis testing was conducted using the *p-value* test on each influence path between the dependent variable and the independent variable. The results of the hypothesis testing are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Results of Direct Effect Hypothesis Testing

Independent	Dependent Variable	Path	P Value	Description
E-Filing System (X1)	Taxpayer	0.351	0.000	Significant
E-Filing System (X1)	Tax Volunteers (M)	0.177	0.002	Significant
Tax Knowledge (X2)	Taxpayer Compliance(Y)	0.194	0.010	Significant
Tax Knowledge (X2)	Tax Volunteers (M)	0.807	0.000	Significant
Tax Volunteers (M)	Taxpayer Compliance(Y)	0.493	0.000	Significant

Source: Primary data processed in 2025

a) The e-filing system affects taxpayer compliance

The results of hypothesis testing analysis using the WarpPLS Structural Equation Modeling approach produced a direct influence coefficient of the e-filing system on taxpayer compliance of 0.351 and a *p-value* of 0.000. Because the *p-value* is < 5%, the hypothesis that the tax e-filing system has a direct and significant effect on taxpayer compliance is accepted. Because the coefficient is positive and significant, it can be concluded that the influence between the two is unidirectional, meaning that the better the e-filing system, the higher the taxpayer compliance will be.

b) Tax knowledge affects taxpayer compliance

The coefficient for the direct influence of taxpayer knowledge on taxpayer compliance is 0.194 and the *p-value* is 0.010. Since the *p-value* is < 5%, the hypothesis that taxpayer

knowledge has a direct effect on taxpayer compliance is accepted. Because the coefficient is positive and significant, it can be concluded that the influence between the two is proportional, meaning that better taxpayer knowledge can significantly increase taxpayer compliance.

c) Tax volunteers have a significant effect on taxpayer compliance

The results of hypothesis testing analysis using the WarpPLS Structural Equation Modeling approach produced a direct influence coefficient of tax volunteers on taxpayer compliance with a value of 0.493 and a *p-value* of 0.000. Because the *p-value* is < 5%, the hypothesis that tax volunteers have a direct and significant effect on taxpayer compliance can be accepted. Because the coefficient is positive and significant, it can be concluded that the influence between the two is unidirectional, meaning that the better the tax volunteers are, the higher the taxpayer compliance will be.

d) E-filing has a significant effect on tax volunteers

The results of hypothesis testing analysis using the WarpPLS Structural Equation Modeling approach produced a direct influence coefficient of the e-filing system on tax volunteers with a value of 0.177 and a *p-value* of 0.002. Because the *p-value* is < 5%, the hypothesis that the tax e-filing system has a direct and significant effect on tax volunteers is accepted. Because the coefficient is positive and significant, it can be concluded that the influence between the two is unidirectional, meaning that the better the e-filing system, the more tax volunteers will increase.

e) Tax knowledge has a significant effect on tax volunteers.

The results of hypothesis testing analysis using the WarpPLS Structural Equation Modeling approach produced a direct influence coefficient of taxpayer knowledge on tax volunteers of 0.807 and a *p-value* of 0.000. Because the *p-value* is < 5%, the hypothesis that taxpayer knowledge has a direct effect on tax volunteers is accepted. Because the coefficient is positive and significant, it can be concluded that the influence between the two is unidirectional, meaning that better taxpayer knowledge can increase the assistance of tax volunteers in supporting the DGT program.

Results of the t-bootstrapping statistical test for indirect effects

Table 9: Results of Indirect Effect Hypothesis Testing

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Mediating Variable	Path Coefficient	P Value	Description
E-Filing System (X1)	Taxpayer Compliance (Y)	Tax Volunteers (M)	0.087	0.007	Significant
Tax Knowledge Tax (X2)	Taxpayer Compliance (Y)	Tax Volunteers (M)	0.398	0.000	Significant

Source: Primary data processed in 2025

a) Tax volunteers mediate the effect of e-filing on taxpayer compliance

The results of hypothesis testing analysis using the WarpPLS Structural Equation Modeling approach produced a path coefficient for the indirect influence of the e-filing system on

taxpayer compliance through tax volunteers. The analysis results obtained a path coefficient value of 0.351 and a p -value = 0.000 between the e-filing system and tax volunteers, while between tax volunteers and taxpayer compliance, a path coefficient value of 0.493 and a p -value = 0.000 were obtained. From the multiplication of the two path coefficients, the magnitude of the indirect effect was obtained, which was 0.087. Because the direct effect value was smaller (0.177) than the indirect effect value (0.087), the hypothesis that the effect of the e-filing system on taxpayer compliance was mediated by tax volunteers was accepted.

b) Tax volunteers mediate the effect of taxpayer knowledge on taxpayer compliance.

The results of hypothesis testing analysis using the WarpPLS Structural Equation Modeling approach produced a path coefficient of the indirect effect of tax knowledge on taxpayer compliance through taxpayer awareness. The analysis results obtained a path coefficient value of 0.194 and a p -value = 0.010 between tax knowledge and tax volunteers, while between tax volunteers and taxpayer compliance, a path coefficient value of 0.493 and a p -value = 0.000 were obtained. From the multiplication of the two path coefficients, the magnitude of the indirect effect is obtained, which is 0.398. Because the direct effect value is smaller (0.194) than the indirect effect value, the hypothesis of the effect of tax knowledge on taxpayer compliance mediated by tax volunteers is accepted.

DISCUSSION

Based on the analysis results, the hypothesis that the e-filing system has a positive effect on taxpayer compliance is accepted. Thus, the first hypothesis is proven. The results of this study indicate that the *e-filing* system that is implemented tends to make it easier for taxpayers to file their taxes.

With *e-filing*, taxpayers no longer need to wait in long queues at Dropbox locations or Tax Offices (KPP). This is one of the new breakthroughs in tax return reporting launched by the DGT to make it easier and more convenient for taxpayers to fulfill their tax obligations, thereby increasing tax compliance. The results of this study are in line with studies conducted by Tasmilah (2021), Ersania & Merkusiwati (2018), Putri & Harimurti (2017), and Avianto et al. (2016), which show similar results.

Based on the analysis results, the hypothesis that taxpayer knowledge has a positive effect on taxpayer compliance is accepted. Thus, the second hypothesis is proven. The results of this study indicate that taxpayer knowledge affects taxpayer compliance. These results show that the higher the taxpayer knowledge, the higher the taxpayer compliance, which certainly has a positive impact on state revenue from the taxation sector. Conversely, the lower the knowledge and understanding of taxes, the lower the tax compliance. This also shows that taxpayers with a high level of knowledge find it easier to understand the applicable taxation system and can apply what they understand. Tax knowledge and understanding are also the objectives of developing the full potential of taxpayers so that they can be good citizens by responsibly paying their taxes. The results of this study are in line with the results of a study conducted by (Setiyani et al., 2018), which states that taxpayer knowledge shows a significant positive

relationship with taxpayer compliance. This is also supported by other researchers such as (Adam et al., 2021; Khasanah & Yushita, 2016; Oktaviani et al., 2020; H. Purba, 2021), who state that taxpayer knowledge has a significant effect on taxpayer compliance. Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that taxpayer knowledge has a significant effect on taxpayer compliance. This means that taxpayers who have a high level of tax knowledge will be able to fulfill their tax obligations easily, thereby increasing the level of tax compliance. Based on the analysis results, the hypothesis that tax volunteers have a positive effect on taxpayer compliance is accepted, so the third hypothesis is accepted. The results of this study show that tax volunteers influence taxpayer compliance.

The results of testing this hypothesis show that the higher the knowledge of tax volunteers, the higher the increase in taxpayer compliance. The higher the tax knowledge of a taxpayer, the more likely they are to develop an attitude of compliance in paying taxes, thereby increasing taxpayer compliance and public trust (Abbas *et al.*, 2020).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis, hypothesis testing, and discussion of the research results described in the previous chapter, it can be concluded that:

- 1) The e-filing system affects taxpayer compliance. This shows that the *e-filing* system tends to make it easier for taxpayers to file their taxes.
- 2) Taxpayers' knowledge affects taxpayer compliance. This shows that the higher the knowledge possessed by taxpayers, the higher their compliance will be.
- 3) The e-filing system affects tax volunteers.
- 4) Tax knowledge influences tax volunteers.
- 5) Tax volunteers have an impact on taxpayer compliance. This shows that the greater the knowledge of tax volunteers in assisting the government through the DGT, the higher the taxpayer compliance will be.
- 6) The e-filing system influences taxpayer compliance and can be mediated by tax volunteers. This shows that the presence of tax volunteers can help taxpayers in reporting their monthly and annual tax returns, thereby ensuring that taxpayers comply with their tax obligations.
- 7) Taxpayers' knowledge influences taxpayer compliance, which can be mediated by tax volunteers. This shows that taxpayers' knowledge can increase tax volunteers' insight in carrying out tax activities and socialization, which has an impact on increasing taxpayer compliance.

The results of this study can provide implications for tax officials and policy makers in the field of taxation to consider the factors that influence the level of taxpayer compliance in this study. This is important because understanding these factors can help increase taxpayer compliance, which will certainly have an impact on increasing state revenue from the taxation sector.

References

- 1) Adnyana, I. M. D., & Yuesti, A. (2020a). The Effect of Applying e-SPT, invoicing, and e- Filing Against Taxpayer Compliance at the East Denpasar Pratama Tax Service Office. *Journal of Management Info*, 7(3), 156–167. <https://doi.org/10.31580/jmi.v7i3.1548>
- 2) Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- 3) Allingham, M. G., & Sandmo, A. (1972). Income tax evasion: A theoretical analysis. *Journal of Public Economics*, 1(3–4), 323–338. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2727\(72\)90010-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2727(72)90010-2)
- 4) Amran, A. (2018). The Effect of Tax Sanctions, Income Level, and Taxpayer Awareness on Individual Taxpayer Compliance. *ATESTASI: Scientific Journal of Accounting*, 1(1), 1-15.
- 5) Anakotta, F. M., Sapulette, S. G., & Iskandar, T. E. (2023). The Effect of E-Filing System Implementation and Tax Understanding on Taxpayer Compliance with the Role of Tax Volunteers as Moderating Variables. *Accounting Research Unit (ARU Journal)*, <https://doi.org/10.30598/arujournalvol4iss1pp48-66>
- 6) Anisa, R., & Suprajitno, D. (2020). The Effect of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and Taxpayer Satisfaction on the Use of E-Filing by Taxpayers in Kebumen. *Journal of Management, Business, and Accounting Students*, 1(1), 595–609. <https://doi.org/10.21831/nominal.v1i1.988>
- 7) Aryobimo, Tri et al. 2012. The Influence of Taxpayers' Perceptions of Fiscal Service Quality on Taxpayer Compliance with Taxpayer Financial Conditions and Risk Preferences as Moderating Variables (An Empirical Study of Individual Taxpayers in Semarang City). [Diponegoro Journal of Accounting, Volume 1, No. 1, Year 2012, p. 2]. Semarang: Diponegoro University
- 8) Daeng, R. R., & Mahmudi. (2022). The effect of the use of E-Filing, E-Billing, ESPT, and E- Bupot on taxpayer compliance. *Proceedings of the National Conference on Accounting* <https://doi.org/10.20885/ncf.vol4.art3>
- 9) Darmayasa, I. Nyoman, Bagus Putra Wibawa, and Ketut Nurhayanti. 2020. "E-Filing and Tax Volunteers in Improving Individual Taxpayer Compliance." *Journal of Accounting Studies* 4(2):208. doi: 10.33603/jka.v4i2.3949
- 10) Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>
- 11) Dewi, L. P., & Merkusiwati, N. K. (2018). The Effect of Taxpayer Awareness, Tax Sanctions, E-Filing, and Tax Amnesty on Taxpayer Reporting Compliance. *E-Journal of Accounting*, Udayana University
- 12) Djo, K. Y. W. (2022). The Effect of Information Technology Utilization, Tax Socialization, and E-Filing Implementation on Taxpayer Compliance. *Accounting Literacy Journal*, 2(2), 119–128. <https://doi.org/10.55587/jla.v2i2.49>
- 13) Ghozali, I. (2021). *Partial Least Squares: Concepts, Techniques, and Applications Using the SmartPLS 3.2.9 Program for Empirical Research* (3rd ed.). Diponegoro University, Semarang.
- 14) Indriani Rahayu NingTyas; Application of E-Filing as an Effort to Improve Compliance of Individual Taxpayers in Submitting Annual Income Tax Returns at the Directorate General of Taxes Headquarters for the Period 2021 to 2023; DOI: 10.31334/transparansi/ v7i1.4323
- 15) Kesumasari, N. K. I., and Suardana, K. A. 2018. "The Influence of Tax Knowledge, Awareness, and Knowledge of Tax Amnesty on Taxpayer Compliance at the Gianyar Tax Office." *E-Journal of Accounting*, Udayana University, ISSN: 2302-8556, Vol. 22, No. 2, pp.1503–1529.
- 16) Kirchler, E., Hoelzl, E., & Wahl, I. (2008). Enforced versus voluntary tax compliance: The “slippery slope” framework. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 29(2), 210–225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joep.2007.02.004>

- 17) Melvinal & Djeni Indrajati Widjaja²; The Role of Tax Volunteers In Serving Taxpayers at The Jakarta Tamansari Tax Office; *Serina Abdimas Journal*; Vol. 2, No. 2, May 2024: pp. 505-510; ISSN-L 2986-6065
- 18) Night, S., & Bananuka, J. (2020). The mediating role of adoption of an electronic tax system in the relationship between attitude towards electronic tax system and tax compliance. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Science*, 25(49), 73–88. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEFAS-07-2018-0066> — (evidence of mediation of e-tax adoption on compliance — relevant to the argument of mediation of e-filing/volunteers)
- 19) Nkundabanyanga, S. K., Mvura, P., Nyamuyonjo, D., Opiso, J., & Nakabuye, Z. (2017). Tax compliance in a developing country: Understanding taxpayers' compliance decision by their perceptions. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 44(6), 931–957. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JES-03-2016-0061> — (study in a developing country: perception factors, relevant to the discussion of digitization and compliance)
- 20) Saptono, P. B., Hodžić, S., Khozen, I., Mahmud, G., Pratiwi, I., Purwanto, D., Aditama, M. A., Haq, N., & Khodijah, S. (2023). Quality of e-tax system and tax compliance intention: The mediating role of user satisfaction. *Informatics*, 10(1), Article 22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/informatics10010022> — (empirical study of e-tax/e-filing; supports discussion on the quality of the e-filing system & the mediation of user satisfaction)
- 21) Yamen, A., Coskun, A., & Mersni, H. (2023). Digitalization and tax evasion: The moderation effect of corruption. *Economic Research — Ekonomska Istraživanja*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2022.2142634>